

Citizen volunteers' disclosure request and web database for post-vaccination deaths among 4 million mRNA COVID-19 vaccine recipients in Japan: A massive wave of deaths occurring months after vaccination, amplified and prolonged by frequent dosing

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Keyword

COVID-19 vaccines, mRNA vaccine, excess mortality, wave of deaths

Abbreviations

coronavirus disease 2019, COVID-19; World Health Organization, WHO

Abstract

While mass vaccination campaigns of COVID-19 vaccines slowed after the 3rd dose in Europe and the United States, Japan continued its world-leading vaccination program, including up to eight doses by 2024. Since the start of COVID-19 vaccinations in 2021, Japan has experienced significant excess mortality. Despite government agencies holding data on vaccination status and deaths among vaccine recipients, the entire scope of potential vaccine-related harm remained unclear. Citizen volunteers collected data from municipalities nationwide, totaling 17,545,662 doses administered to 4,025,948 individuals in the retrospective cohort study. Notably, mortality rates sharply increased several months after vaccination. Furthermore, multiple doses correlated with increased mortality; each additional dose led to earlier deaths and prolonged periods of elevated mortality. The massive deaths associated with vaccination may have been overlooked until now because the majority of deaths have occurred not immediately after vaccination, but several months later. The total number of Japanese individuals who died within one year of vaccination between 2021 and 2024 was estimated to be approximately 3.89 million. While this figure does not necessarily represent the number of people who died directly from the COVID-19 vaccination, it suggests that far more lives were impacted by the vaccine than commonly believed. It raises the possibility that the COVID-19 vaccine caused accelerated aging in Japanese individuals, potentially leading to death at an earlier age than their natural lifespan. The web database of the “COVID-19 Vaccine Data Disclosure Request Project” is publicly available at:

https://stop-mrna.sakura.ne.jp/db/home_en.php

Introduction

The novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) was first reported in Wuhan, China, in December 2019, and the causative virus, SARS-CoV-2, was identified shortly thereafter(1). The World Health Organization (WHO) declared a global pandemic on March 11, 2020. Japan began COVID-19 vaccinations on February 17, 2021, initially prioritizing healthcare and essential workers (2). Vaccinations for seniors started on April 12, 2021, and the target population was gradually expanded to include those with underlying medical conditions and the general public (2). By October 2024, Japan had administered up to 8 doses per person, achieving the world's highest COVID-19 vaccination rate (2). In 2020, before the COVID pandemic began and vaccination became widespread, Japan experienced no excess mortality(2,3). However, in 2021, coinciding with the start of COVID-19 vaccinations, a significant excess mortality occurred(2,3). Excess deaths have been reported in European countries since the pandemic period (4-7). While it cannot be ruled out that excess deaths during the COVID-19 pandemic were caused directly or indirectly by COVID-19 infection, this nonetheless raises the possibility that either the effectiveness of COVID-19 vaccines in preventing infection and severe illness was limited, or that the vaccines themselves may have caused adverse effects. Under Japan's relief system for injury to health with vaccination (based on the Vaccination Law), as of December 2025, over 9,000 COVID-19 vaccine-related cases have been certified, including more than 1,000 deaths. However, the Japanese government's recognition of vaccine-related harm remains limited. Citizens who witnessed the deaths of family members or acquaintances after vaccination became concerned about potential adverse events, leading to the formation of citizen volunteer groups. To uncover the reality of vaccine-related harm, we filed disclosure requests with municipalities and collected records from across Japan.

This investigation identified serious, previously unrecognized adverse events following COVID-19 vaccination, specifically a significant increase in mortality months after administration. We aim to raise concerns about the long-term safety of mRNA vaccines to urge caution about the continued expansion of these platforms.

Materials and Methods

Disclosure request for post-vaccination deaths

Hundreds of citizen volunteers from the disclosure request team of the United Citizens for Stopping mRNA Vaccines and the Yukoku Union submitted disclosure requests for post-vaccination deaths to municipalities. The requested information items included: (1) date of birth or age at data collection (if not provided, age range in 10-year increments such as teens or twenties), (2) vaccination date, lot number, and dose number, (3) date of death, (4) date of

moving out (if applicable), (5) date of moving in (if applicable), (6) gender, and (7) the above items for individuals without vaccination records. Upon receipt, the data underwent standardization to address inconsistencies in annotation, conversion to a uniform date format, and verification of chronological plausibility, such as ensuring that vaccination dates did not precede dates of death or migration. Records demonstrating internal inconsistencies or implausible chronological order were excluded prior to inclusion in the database. Despite these validation steps, potential biases may persist due to varying data quality, inconsistent reporting standards across municipalities, and incomplete information for some individuals.

Data collection

Individuals who moved in were excluded because their vaccination records from their previous residence were unknown. Individuals who moved out were also excluded because subsequent vaccination records or deaths could not be tracked. The age at vaccination initiation was calculated from the date of birth, year of birth, and age at data acquisition, and used to classify generations: <20 years (young); 20–69 years (working-age); >70 years (senior). For each lot number, vaccination date, and date of death, the total number of vaccinations, number of deaths, mortality rate, and the number of days from the last vaccination to death were calculated by lot, generation, number of doses, and target variant. Among the results of the disclosure request, data including vaccination records for individuals, the age of vaccinated individuals and those without vaccination records, the date of death if deceased, the date of out-migration if out-migrated, the date of in-migration if in-migrated, and gender were treated as complete data. When the age of individuals without vaccination records was inaccurate, the data were treated as semi-complete. Those data were analyzed in this study.

The disclosure requests pertained to the special, exceptional temporary COVID-19 vaccination program from the 1st to the 7th dose. Consequently, some municipalities that disclosed information were unable to track regular vaccinations administered after the 7th dose. This particularly affected the capture of death counts from the 7th dose onwards, which occurred during the later phase of the temporary vaccination program.

This retrospective cohort study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. All data were anonymized, and patient privacy and confidentiality were strictly protected.

Database construction

The database uses MySQL, and the website was built using Apache and PHP. The disclosure data obtained from each municipality contained inconsistencies in annotation, missing values, and discrepancies. Therefore, data cleaning was performed before import, and the data was formatted as CSV for database insertion using Python scripts. This database primarily handles reference operations, but due to its massive data volume, it is necessary to reduce the load on display and aggregation. Therefore, intermediate (aggregate) tables were created for specific purposes to ensure efficient reference performance.

Mortality rates

The simple mortality rate was calculated as the proportion of deaths per week relative to the cohort at the start of observation—specifically, the entire group of individuals who received a specific number of doses. The simple mortality rate directly reflects the scale of deaths because its denominator remains constant. While interval-specific mortality rates were calculated using the person-week method as the proportion of deaths per week among survivors who received a specific number of doses, it is important to note that individuals who proceed to the next vaccination dose are excluded from the group that received that dose as their final vaccination. The interval-specific mortality rate tends to increase sharply as more people advance to the next vaccination, making it a better indicator of mortality among those who did not continue vaccination.

Use of AI

ChatGPT was used to generate aggregation scripts and website source code.

Results

Grassroots volunteer-driven data disclosure request for post-vaccination deaths

In Japan, COVID-19 vaccination began in February 2021 (Fig. 1A). The first dose was followed by the 2nd dose in March 2021, and the 3rd dose in December of the same year. Subsequent doses were administered, culminating in the 8th dose, introduced for the general public in 2024 (2) (Fig. 1A). During this vaccination campaign, vaccine types evolved to match the prevailing COVID-19 variants. Initial vaccines targeted the original Wuhan variant, while subsequent doses were modified to target Omicron variants BA.1, BA.4/5, XBB.1.5, and JN.1. While Omicron spike proteins are known for their high mutation rates (8), potentially affecting antigenicity and function, the XBB.1.5 and JN.1 vaccines were administered to the general public in Japan for the first time without sufficient clinical trials (2). Despite lacking an established safety profile, Japan also began administering the world's first self-amplifying mRNA vaccine to the general public in 2024 (2) (Fig. 1A).

To investigate post-vaccination deaths, hundreds of volunteers submitted data disclosure requests to municipalities across Japan (Fig. 1B). Cooperation with disclosure requests varied significantly among municipalities. Of the requests submitted to 191 municipalities out of Japan's approximately 1,700 municipalities, 57 municipalities disclosed the information, enabling analysis. Ultimately, data from 4,100,806 vaccine recipients (17,647,512 doses administered) were registered in the database (as of November 2025), of which 4,025,948 (17,545,662 doses administered) were used for statistical analysis (Fig. 1C).

Web database of post-vaccination death cases

Fig. 2 shows information published in the web database of the “COVID-19 Vaccine Data Disclosure Request Project” (https://stop-mrna.sakura.ne.jp/db/home_en.php). This database records the final vaccine lot administered to deceased individuals. Users can search for lots with high case counts, high mortality rates, deaths occurring immediately after vaccination, or lot-specific data (Fig. 2A). As of November 2025, the database recorded 17,647,512 doses and 221,014 post-vaccination deaths (Fig. 2B). Examples of the top 10 lots are shown in Fig. 2C, 2D, and 2E, while examples of lots 11th–100th are shown in Table S1, S2, and S3. Among lots with fewer doses administered, some, like lot HG5938, reached a mortality rate of 71.429% (Fig. 2C). The top 10 lots by mortality rate exceeded 12%. A disproportionately greater number of deaths, ~ 3,000, are recorded for decedents receiving doses from four specific lots (Fig. 2D). Ten people, who received a dose from Lot FM3289, died on the day of or the day after vaccination. It was also found that more than 10 lots have 3 or more vaccine recipients, who died on the day of or the day after vaccination (Fig. 2E).

Impact of lot differences on mortality

The database tracks the vaccination timing for each lot, as well as the subsequent timing and number of deaths. Most lots were administered in a concentrated manner within a short period. For example, lot FP9647 was administered between June and August 2022 (Fig. 3A, top left). While the vaccination dates of the deceased overlapped with this period (Fig. 3A, top right), the death dates were distributed from August 2022 to June 2024 (Fig. 3A, bottom left). Counting from each recipient's vaccination date, the number of deaths peaked approximately 4 months post-vaccination and then gradually declined (Fig. 3A bottom right). Classifying by number of doses, cases from lot FP9647 were administered during the 4th-dose period, likely explaining the higher number of deaths among 4th-dose recipients (Fig. 3B). The distribution of death dates varied by lot. For example, in lot GJ2675, deaths peaked 2–5 months after vaccination and then gradually decreased (Fig. 3C left). In contrast, for lot HG2273, the peak in deaths began

approximately 2 months after vaccination, and the high mortality rate persisted for over a year (Fig. 3C right).

Regarding vaccine variant classification, each vaccine type was concentrated in specific time periods (Fig. S1). The Wuhan-type vaccine was administered from 2021 to 2022. Subsequently, vaccination shifted to BA.1, BA.4/5, and XBB.1.5 variants in 2023, and to JN.1 in 2024. Mortality peaks appeared several months after vaccination for the Wuhan-type, BA.1, and BA.4/5. However, for the XBB.1.5-targeted vaccine used in Japan's 7th vaccination round, a prolonged wave of deaths followed vaccination (Fig. S1). Although the analysis period was insufficient in this study, a trend of increasing mortality over time after vaccination was also observed for JN.1.

We analyzed the vaccine lot administered to individuals who died after vaccination. Some lots were administered over 200,000 times, while many others were used only once or a few times. Therefore, to clarify the probability of receiving each high-risk lot, we analyzed the number of deaths and mortality rates within 1 year post-vaccination for each lot, based on the number of doses administered per lot rather than the number of lots. Among all vaccinations, the probability of receiving a lot resulting in more than 2,000 deaths within 1 year after the final dose was 16.4%. The probability of receiving a lot resulting in 1,000–2,000 deaths was 28.7%, and 19.0% for lots resulting in 200–499 deaths (Fig. 3D left). Thus, the probability of receiving a lot resulting in 200 or more deaths within one year post-vaccination reached 85.4%. The probability of receiving a lot with a mortality rate of 2% or higher within 1 year after vaccination was 4.4%, including a 0.1% probability of receiving a lot with a mortality rate of 5% or higher (data not shown). Meanwhile, the probability of receiving a lot with a mortality rate of 1% to 2% was 30.5%, and that of 0.5% to 1% was 40.9% (Fig. 3D right). The total probability of receiving a lot with a mortality rate of 0.5% or higher within one year after vaccination was 75.8%.

Standardization for estimating post-vaccination deaths across Japan

Our analysis included 4,025,948 individuals who received the 1st dose, 4,004,076 who received the 2nd dose, and 3,406,171 who received the 3rd dose. Japan's special temporary COVID-19 vaccination program ended on March 31, 2024. By that date, the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare reported nationwide totals of 104,761,469 1st-dose recipients, 103,473,276 2nd-dose recipients, and 86,700,808 3rd-dose recipients(9). These figures are presumed to have remained essentially unchanged, as our analysis shows that new vaccinations among non-vaccinated individuals became extremely rare after November 2021, as discussed later. These figures

represent 26.0, 25.8, and 25.5 times the data from this disclosure request, with an average of 25.8 ± 0.29 times. Thus, multiplying the disclosure request data by 25.8 allows us to estimate the entire Japanese population, enabling us to infer the number of 4th to 8th doses administered in Japan.

Among those vaccinated, 21.9% stopped after 3rd doses, the largest group, followed by 19.6% who stopped after 4th doses. Those stopping after the 2nd or 5th doses were the next most common. Only 1.2% stopped after 1st dose, an extremely low figure. This may reflect exceptional circumstances in which individuals accepted the vaccine but could not accept the subsequent 2nd dose, for example, due to health hazards.

Data on the 8th dose were extremely limited. One reason is that the disclosure request targeted COVID-19 special, exceptional, temporary vaccination up to the 7th dose; the 8th dose, administered as part of the regular vaccination schedule, was not originally covered by the request. Furthermore, when disclosure requests began, the 8th dose was not yet widely administered, resulting in an insufficient observation period for those who received it. Consequently, subsequent analyses were limited to those who received up to 7th doses. Additionally, some municipalities did not exclude data on the 8th dose (administered as part of the regular vaccination schedule) from their 7th-dose data. This suggests that some of the 7th-dose fatalities may have included individuals who had received the 8th dose.

Overview of post-vaccination death cases

To visualize the complete picture of post-vaccination deaths over more than four years, we employed a heatmap. Each point represents a specific vaccination date (x-axis) and is positioned based on the number of days from the final vaccination to death (y-axis) (Fig. 4A). The red and orange clusters indicate days with a high number of deaths, occurring seven times: after the 1st and 2nd doses in June 2021, the 3rd dose in March 2022, the 4th dose in August-September 2022, the 5th dose in December 2022, the 6th dose in June 2023, and the 7th dose in December 2023. The peak in deaths appeared to occur not immediately after vaccination, but rather several months after vaccination, with a sustained period of high mortality. This prolonged period of mass mortality was particularly evident after the 5th and 7th doses. These periods of mass mortality occurred regardless of season or vaccination timing. These patterns were consistent across regional cities, particularly evident in densely populated cities like Sagamihara and Kagoshima, but also observed in less populous cities such as Toyohashi, Akashi, Itami, and Toyokawa (Fig. 4B).

Frequent vaccinations prolong waves of massive deaths following vaccination.

Figure 5A shows the number of days after the first vaccination at which each vaccine recipient died, along with the number of doses administered. We first analyzed simple mortality rates, calculated as a proportion of weekly deaths among the total number of vaccine recipients (4,025,948) obtained through disclosure requests (Fig. 5A, left axis). The simple mortality rate directly reflects the scale of deaths because it is proportional to the total number of deaths among those who have received that dose. Furthermore, the actual observed number of deaths was multiplied by 25.8 based on Table 1 and normalized to the estimated number of deaths for all of Japan (Fig. 5, right axis). The mortality rate among vaccine recipients rose after the initial vaccination began in February 2021. Subsequently, the mortality rate appears relatively stable, excluding possibly seasonal increases in winter. On the other hand, the breakdown reveals that it consisted of overlapping, complex patterns of deaths occurring after each vaccination dose (Fig. 5A). Japan did not experience excess mortality in 2020 when the COVID-19 pandemic began; large-scale excess mortality occurred only after COVID-19 vaccinations started in 2021 (Fig. S2). The annual mortality rate in 2020—before vaccination began and during the height of the pandemic—was 1.1%(3), corresponding to a weekly mortality rate of 0.021% (Fig. 5A). Thus, mortality rates after COVID-19 vaccination initiation generally exceeded pre-vaccination rates.

Next, we analyzed the number of days after each individual's final vaccination until death (Fig. 5B). The simple mortality rate (left axis) was calculated as the ratio of weekly deaths to the total number of vaccine recipients (fixed population) who received a specific number of doses. The estimated number of deaths across Japan is shown on the right axis (Fig. 5B). Most deaths following the 1st dose occurred within a few weeks of vaccination, possibly because most individuals received their second dose shortly after the first. In contrast, the peak for the 2nd dose occurred approximately 7 months after vaccination, for the 3rd dose approximately 3-4 months, and for the 4th to 7th doses approximately 3 months later. Notably, a phenomenon of elevated mortality in waves, termed "waves of deaths," was observed. While the simple mortality rate, being proportional to the number of deaths, reflects the scale of deaths, it was estimated that during the peak of the 2nd-dose wave, for example, nearly 30,000 people were dying weekly across Japan (the peaks of the waves are highlighted with red triangles). It is important to note that individuals who proceed to the next vaccination dose are supposed to leave the group that received that vaccination as their final dose, potentially affecting the apparent decline in the wave of deaths.

The peak of the mortality rate occurred earlier with each additional dose. Although mortality declined after each peak, persistent waves of deaths continued after the 4th dose, with post-peak rates remaining at high levels. Particularly noteworthy is that the mortality peak (approximately 3 months post-vaccination), which occurred after the 7th dose, persisted for over a year (highlighted by the red bar). Weekly mortality rates peaked at 0.01% after the 1st dose, 0.02% after the 2nd and 3rd doses, 0.03% after the 4th dose, and 0.04% after the 5th and 6th doses. After the 7th dose, the rate exceeded 0.05% and persisted for over a year. Looking at the combined data from the 1st to 7th doses, it is clear that the majority of deaths were among the seniors. However, the peak in deaths did not occur immediately after vaccination, but was delayed by approximately 4 months. It was estimated that, around four months after vaccination, deaths nationwide reached approximately 100,000 per week (Fig. 5B). In summary, as the number of doses increased, the mortality wave became higher, peaked earlier, and decayed more slowly. The 7th dose showed particularly high and persistently elevated mortality rates. However, it is important to note that the 7th-dose deaths partially included individuals who had also received an 8th dose.

Furthermore, analyzing the 7th-dose recipients by generation revealed that the majority of deaths occurred among the senior (Fig. 5C left), with the mortality wave for the seniors closely approximating the overall pattern (7th in Fig. 5B). Meanwhile, the mortality rate for the 7th dose among the working-age population was lower than that among the senior, but the wave pattern was similar to that of the senior (Fig. 5C center). Decomposing and overlaying the wave patterns of the total 7 doses in Fig. 5A reconstituted a massive wave of deaths (Fig. 5C right).

The death scale of post-COVID-19 vaccination in Japan

Based on the trend of the wave of deaths, we could infer that deaths correlated with COVID-19 vaccination were more likely to occur several months or later after vaccination. However, an unrestricted analysis would include many deaths occurring at the natural end of life. Therefore, we analyzed mortality rates and estimated the number of deaths within 1 year after the final vaccine dose. The mortality rate within 1 year of COVID-19 vaccination varied significantly across generations, with the working-age population showing approximately 10 times higher rates than the young, and the seniors showing approximately 10 times higher rates than the working-age population (Fig. 6A, left). Notably, the mortality rate tended to increase with each additional dose: 0.088% for the 1st dose, 0.88% for the 2nd, 0.80% for the 3rd, 0.98% for the 4th, 1.4% for the 5th, 1.5% for the 6th, and 2.5% for the 7th (Fig. 6A right). Multiply the number of deaths actually observed by 25.8, based on the normalization value in Table 1, and the estimated number of deaths within one year of vaccination among Japanese individuals was

2,967 in the young age group, 368,476 in the working-age group, and 3,518,888 in the senior group, totaling approximately 3,890,330 (Fig. 6B).

Discussion

The large-scale grassroots movement investigating post-vaccination deaths in this study is unprecedented worldwide. Japan's COVID-19 vaccination program (17.6 million doses across 8 rounds) was analyzed through information disclosure requests targeting Japanese municipalities (Fig. 1). Despite administrative authorities holding death data on vaccine recipients, this information has not been analyzed or reported. As a limitation of our disclosure request, we were unable to obtain the mortality data for the unvaccinated population itself, nor could we obtain data comparing healthy individuals with those who were not. Consequently, it was difficult to employ standard epidemiological methods comparing vaccinated and unvaccinated individuals or healthy and unhealthy individuals. Nevertheless, the large-scale post-vaccination mortality data still revealed numerous new findings. Massive deaths occurred months after vaccination, and the number of deaths within one year of vaccination was estimated at approximately 3.89 million. This demonstrated waves of long-term post-vaccination deaths and the cumulative harm from frequent vaccinations. We share these data publicly through a public web database.

Significant differences in mortality rates and death counts were confirmed among vaccine lots (Figs. 2 and 3). This supports a Danish study(10) showing that the number of adverse events varies significantly among lots, with high-risk lots exhibiting a higher frequency of serious adverse events. While the high-risk lots reported to date have been associated with elevated short-term mortality, our study identified lots with elevated long-term mortality (Fig. 2). Furthermore, lots with high short-term mortality rates and lots with high long-term mortality rates were generally distinct lots, with the latter type contributing significantly to the total number of deaths (Fig. 3). Differences in mortality between administered lots are most likely due to variations in the quantity or quality of vaccine components. One example: recent reports indicate substantial contamination of COVID-19 vaccines with DNA from the templates used for RNA transcription, and lots with higher DNA contamination tended to have higher adverse event frequencies(11). While pseudouridine-modified RNA is prone to ribosomal slippage, leading to translation errors (12), RNA integrity in COVID-19 vaccines varies across vials (13), and low RNA quality may result in the production of abnormal proteins.

During the COVID-19 pandemic in Japan, lockdown-like policies were not implemented. Strict controls, such as prohibiting access to public transportation, postal services, or government administrative services without proof of vaccination, or barring entry to workplaces or schools, were not enforced. Thus, unvaccinated individuals could continue their daily lives in Japan. Because situations requiring proof of vaccination were limited, Japan did not adopt measures like vaccine passports to verify vaccination status. Comparing the number of deaths among the unvaccinated to the number of deaths among the vaccinated is crucial for estimating the number of deaths caused by COVID-19 vaccination. However, even with this recent disclosure request, it proved challenging to do so (Fig. S5). As a scandal has emerged in Japan, where the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare classified individuals with unknown vaccination histories as unvaccinated for statistical purposes (14), even the Japanese government itself might not possess reliable data on the unvaccinated.

The majority of those who died within a year of receiving the COVID-19 vaccination were seniors. Deaths among the seniors are often attributed to age, and deaths among the health-vulnerable, including the seniors with underlying conditions, have generally been overlooked. The peak in deaths following vaccination occurred several months after vaccination (Fig. 5). Unlike deaths immediately after vaccination, linking deaths months later to the vaccine is difficult. In Japan, as of November 2025, COVID-19 vaccinations have reached eight rounds, with overlapping waves of vaccination that were consistently accompanied by high mortality rates. Despite the high mortality, the lack of significant fluctuations in mortality rates (Fig. 5A) may have created a “boiling frog” effect—meaning gradual changes are difficult to notice—, making it difficult to recognize the link with vaccination. Furthermore, diverse causes of death and insufficient understanding of the mRNA vaccine mechanism obscure potential associations.

Waves of high mortality repeatedly occurred several months after COVID-19 vaccination (Figs. 4 and 5), indicating a correlation between these waves and vaccination. As the wave-like pattern appears consistent across regions and seasons (Fig. 4), regional differences or seasonality cannot explain these death waves. The mortality peak occurred approximately 7 months after the 2nd dose, 3-4 months after the 3rd dose, 3 months after the 4th to 6th doses, and 3 months or later after the 7th dose (Fig. 5B). Furthermore, mortality rates in waves of deaths increase with each additional dose, and the periods of high mortality also become longer. Although the wave’s peak was delayed, the wave of deaths was confirmed in interval-specific mortality rates based on the person-week method (Fig. S3, S4). Thus, each additional dose appears to increase the scale and duration of the death wave, likely causing cumulative health damage and potentially shortening healthy life expectancy. While mortality rates decline over time, this

analysis focuses solely on deaths and excludes other health impacts; therefore, the vaccine's potential harmful health effects may persist.

Those who discontinued after the first dose constituted a minority overall, and the period with high interval-specific mortality coincided with a time when the simple mortality rate declined and the absolute number of deaths decreased (Figs. S3 and S4). However, focusing on those who stopped at the 1st or 2nd dose still shows a high mortality rate, suggesting that stopping after the 1st or 2nd dose cannot be considered safe. The extremely high mortality rate among those who stopped after the 1st dose (Figs. S3 and S4) may be due to circumstances specific to 1st-dose recipients. Those who received only the 1st dose were not individuals consciously avoiding vaccination; they had no time to deliberate, as the 2nd dose was scheduled just a few weeks later. Those who stopped after the 1st dose, representing 1.2% of vaccine recipients, might include individuals who experienced severe health complications that prevented them from receiving the 2nd dose. Such individuals might have subsequently become debilitated and died. Indeed, analysis by interval-specific mortality rates shows higher mortality with fewer doses (Fig. S3, S4). This may reflect a situation where the most vulnerable—the very senior or those with underlying conditions—suffered adverse events from fewer vaccine doses and dropped out of the vaccinated cohort.

Most deaths occur months after vaccination, likely due to long-term health damage from mRNA vaccines. Unlike conventional mRNA, vaccine mRNA is stabilized by the methylpseudouridine modification (15,16). Furthermore, COVID-19 vaccines use the full-length spike protein mRNA(17), which induces massive spike protein production. Translation of the spike protein does not cease immediately after vaccination; in fact, detectable levels of spike protein have been reported months to years post-vaccination(18-20). Furthermore, it has become clear that the spike protein itself exhibits vascular toxicity(21), as does the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein. Vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia (VITT)(22), which causes embolisms and thromboses, and cutaneous vasculitis(23) have also been reported in individuals who received COVID-19 vaccines. Indeed, the spike protein has been detected in the blood of adolescents who developed myocarditis after COVID-19 vaccination (24), and vaccine-derived spike protein has been detected in the brain and heart (25). Thrombosis in organs like the brain and heart can lead to sudden death. Thus, there is concern that persistent spike protein expression could trigger a delayed wave of deaths through vascular damage caused by thrombosis or other mechanisms.

The second cause of death, delayed from vaccination, could be the disorder in the immune system, where a time lag is expected from immune system abnormalities to subsequent disease onset and death. In the mechanism of mRNA vaccines, mRNA is translated within cells, and antigens are presented on the cell surface(16). These cells then become targets for immune system attacks, including antibodies (antibody-dependent auto-attack) and T cells (T cell-dependent auto-attack), potentially causing random damage to multiple organs(26). As temporary lymphocyte depletion was reported after vaccination in clinical trials (17), mRNA COVID vaccines strongly stimulate the immune system and may induce immunosuppression as a rebound effect. Vaccines can inherently cause autoimmune diseases(26), and autoimmune diseases have been reported in COVID vaccine recipients(22). Furthermore, excessive immune stimulation induces class switching of antibodies to immunosuppressive subclass, IgG4(27), increasing susceptibility to coronavirus infections(27) and promoting cancer progression(28) (29). As vaccine-derived spike proteins have been detected in metastatic cancers(30), cases of cancer progressing after COVID-19 vaccination have been accumulating(31). While cancer is a disease caused by genomic aberrations, the transmission of mutations induced by residual vaccine DNA(11) to subsequent generations would likely represent the most delayed adverse events of mRNA vaccines.

This study estimated that the total number of deaths occurring within 1 year of vaccination between Feb. 2021 and Nov. 2024 was 3.89 million. As Japan's annual total deaths were 1.44 million (2021), 1.57 million (2022), 1.58 million (2023), and 1.61 million (2024), the total from 2021 to 2024 is 6.19 million, suggesting that approximately two-thirds of these deaths occurred within 1 year of vaccination. This might not be surprising, given that 105 million of Japan's 123 million total population (approximately 85%) have received COVID-19 vaccinations (Table 1), and most deaths among those vaccinated have occurred within 1 year of their final dose (Fig. 4). Japan experienced large-scale excess mortality following the mass rollout of COVID-19 vaccines (Fig. S2A). While estimates vary(2,3), we estimated excess deaths from 2021 to 2024 at approximately 452,000 (Fig. S2B). Thus, the estimated number of deaths within one year of vaccination far exceeds the excess deaths, suggesting post-vaccination deaths were not solely caused by the COVID-19 vaccinations. Nevertheless, it appears that a significantly larger number of people than previously thought have been affected by COVID-19 vaccination. Instead, this suggests that COVID-19 vaccination may be causing premature deaths—that is, many people are dying earlier than their natural lifespan, and this is reflected in the excess deaths. Conditions like myocarditis, autoimmune diseases, and cancer are diseases whose risk increases with aging. As these diseases are also related to the COVID-19 vaccine's mechanism of action(22,24,26,28-31), it is conceivable that its side effects may include accelerated aging.

The seniors suffer more severe consequences from aging, and accelerated aging in the seniors directly leads to death. However, when senior individuals die after receiving the COVID-19 vaccine, the causal relationship is unclear, and such deaths are often attributed to old age or natural lifespan. For the working-age population and younger individuals, even if aging progresses somewhat, they may not die easily thanks to their inherent youth and vitality. Overall, the extent of future health damage and the reduction in healthy life expectancy remain unknown at this time, and further study is necessary to clarify these outcomes.

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Legends to Figures

Fig. 1. Disclosure requests by citizen volunteers for post-COVID-19 vaccine death cases in Japan. **A.** The start of the COVID-19 pandemic and Japan's vaccination schedule. **B.** Status of disclosure requests for post-COVID-19 vaccine death cases in Japan. "In progress" includes cases under negotiation, under review, under a disclosure request, and submitted to the administration. **C.** Flow of disclosure request data analysis.

Fig. 2. Post-COVID-19 vaccine death case database from the disclosure request project.

A. Database input fields. Deaths: top 100 lots by number of deaths. Mortality: the top 100 lots by mortality rate. Short-Term-Mortality: top 100 lots by deaths on the day of vaccination and the day after. Examples of the top 10 lots are shown in C, D, and E. **B.** Death cases for all lots. **C.** Top 10 lots by mortality rate. To avoid overestimating mortality rates, lots with total vaccination counts of 5 or fewer were excluded from the top 100 mortality list. **D.** Top 10 lots by number of deaths. **E.** Top 10 lots by short-term mortality.

Fig. 3. Death cases by vaccine lot. **A.** Using lot FP9647 as an example: Number of vaccinated individuals by vaccination date (top left). Number of deaths by vaccination date (top right). Number of deaths by date of death (bottom left). Number of deaths by days from final

vaccination to death (bottom right) (by age group). **B.** number of deaths by days from final vaccination to death (by number of doses administered). **C.** Example of lots with different death patterns. Number of deaths and days since final vaccination for lots GJ2675 and HG2273 (by age group). Periods with insufficient observation are shaded gray. **D.** Number of deaths within one year after vaccination for each lot and the proportion of the number of doses administered for that lot relative to the total number of doses administered across all lots (left). Mortality rate within one year after vaccination for each lot and the proportion of the number of doses administered for that lot relative to the total number of doses administered across all lots (right). For example, a lot administered 1000 times was counted as 1000, not 1, in the rate calculation. The mortality rate represents the probability of death within one year post-vaccination for individuals who received that lot as the final dose.

Fig. 4. Overview of deaths following COVID-19 vaccination in Japan (A) and in municipalities (B). The horizontal axis shows the date of the final vaccination for each death, and the vertical axis shows the number of days from the final vaccination to death. The color indicates the number of people who received their final vaccination on a specific date and died a specific number of days later. Death clusters occurred after a large number of doses were administered.

Fig. 5. Wave-like distribution of deaths following COVID-19 vaccination. **A.** Weekly simple mortality rate and number of deaths among vaccine recipients since the start of the initial vaccination. Colors indicate each vaccination dose. The blue line shows weekly mortality in 2020, before vaccination began and during the height of the pandemic. Periods with insufficient observation are shaded gray. **B.** Weekly simple mortality rate among all individuals who received a specified number of doses (left axis). The right axis shows the estimated number of deaths in Japan for each vaccination dose. **C.** Weekly simple mortality rates and number of deaths in Japan for the age group (7th dose senior and working-age population) and by final dose number.

Week 0 corresponds to days 0-6 post-vaccination. The left axis shows simple mortality rates relative to the starting population that has received the specified number of doses (i.e., mortality rates per the total number of individuals who have received the specified number of doses in the corresponding graph). The right axis shows the estimated total number of deaths in Japan, calculated by multiplying the observed weekly deaths by the total Japanese normalization factor

of 25.8. The period when the simple mortality rate peaks is highlighted with a red triangle or red bar.

Fig. 6. Mortality rate and number of deaths within one year after final vaccination. A.

The mortality rate is the proportion of deaths occurring within 1 year of the final dose, relative to the total number of individuals who received that dose. **B.** Estimated number of deaths within one year post-vaccination for all vaccinated individuals in Japan. By age group (left) and total number (right), color-coded by final vaccination dose.

Supplementary materials

Excess deaths after COVID-19 vaccine rollout in Japan

In Japan, annual deaths had been increasing year by year, but surprisingly, the annual death count decreased in 2020 when the COVID pandemic began (Fig. S2A). However, annual deaths increased sharply and significantly starting in 2021, after COVID vaccinations began (Fig. S2A). To estimate excess deaths after the start of COVID vaccinations, we fit a linear model to annual deaths from 2010 to 2020, excluding 2011, the year of the Great East Japan Earthquake. Even without adjusting for population differences in mortality rates, this line closely approximated the increase in annual deaths before the start of COVID-19 vaccinations (R-squared value of 0.9688). By comparing against this expected line, excess deaths following the COVID-19 vaccine rollout were estimated (Fig. S2B). The excess deaths in 2020, just before the start of COVID-19 vaccinations, were -16,350. In contrast, excess deaths were 32,562 in 2021, 143,567 in 2022, 132,344 in 2023, and 143,517 in 2024, totaling 451,990 excess deaths from 2021 to 2024.

Post-vaccination deaths among those who discontinued vaccination

In Japan, COVID-19 vaccinations continued through the 8th dose by 2024, but not everyone received them. To analyze the population that discontinued vaccination, interval-specific mortality rates were calculated based on the person-week method (Fig. S3, right (senior); S4, right (all generations)). This method calculates the death rate per week by the number of survivors who received that round of vaccinations as a fluctuating denominator; individuals at specific vaccination stages experience a sharp increase at the particular time point when they advance to the next round of vaccination. This is because the denominator of the interval-

specific mortality rate decreases as those progressing to the next dose are removed from the population, making the mortality rate of those who stopped vaccination apparent. Indeed, the peak of the interval-specific mortality rate (highlighted by the red triangle) (Fig. S3 right) occurred significantly later than the peak of the simple mortality rate (Figure S3, left). Thus, after the peak, the interval-specific mortality rate reflects the mortality of those who stopped vaccination, highlighting their increased vulnerability to death.

Looking at the simple mortality rate with a fixed denominator, for example, mortality among seniors after the 1st dose peaked 14 days post-vaccination and then declined sharply (Fig. S3, top left). In Japan, the 2nd dose was administered a few weeks after the 1st, and most individuals who received the 1st dose also received the 2nd. Thus, the sharp decline in the simple mortality rate among 1st-dose recipients two weeks post-vaccination suggests that most progressed to the next dose, reducing the number of 1st-dose recipients. In contrast, interval-specific mortality rates among 1st-dose recipients showed that mortality among the senior peaked two months after vaccination, reaching 1.2%. Since the total number of deaths among all 1st-dose recipients had already significantly decreased by two months post-vaccination when viewed by simple mortality rate, this indicates a high mortality rate among those who stopped at the 1st dose. This high mortality may be due to individuals who experienced significant adverse events after the 1st dose choosing not to receive the 2nd dose, yet subsequently dying.

A similar trend was observed after the 2nd dose. In interval-specific mortality rates, which tend to highlight those who stopped at that dose, the wave's peak shifted later than in simple mortality rates. For the senior, the peak occurred around 9 months after the 2nd dose and around 7 months after the 3rd to 6th doses. The peak in simple mortality rates may begin to decline after those who proceed to the next dose are removed from the population. However, even in interval-specific mortality rates—which more readily reflect those who stopped vaccination—the mortality rate decreased after the wave peak, though the aftereffects of the mortality wave lingered longer. For the 5th dose and beyond, the elevated mortality rate after the peak persisted for over a year post-vaccination. While these represent a minority of total deaths, these results indicate that individuals who discontinued vaccination at each respective dose also died after a period following vaccination. A similar trend was observed across all age groups combined (Fig. S4 left). Nevertheless, the higher simple mortality rate observed for the combined total of all generations compared to seniors alone from the 5th to 7th doses was thought to be due to the high mortality among the working-age generation who received frequent vaccinations (Fig. 5B).

Is it possible to compare vaccinated and unvaccinated individuals?

To estimate deaths attributable to COVID-19 vaccination, it is crucial to compare the number of deaths among unvaccinated individuals with that among vaccinated individuals. However, the disclosure request did not provide the unvaccinated data itself. Therefore, we first analyzed deaths among individuals without vaccination records, assuming most of them were unvaccinated. The average number of individuals without vaccination records was 1,429,865 (Fig. S5A), calculated as the total number divided by the number of days. The change in mortality rates among individuals without vaccination records did not appear to reflect only the seasonal increase in winter deaths (Fig. S5B). From June to August 2021, the number of senior individuals without vaccination records decreased to 1/10 (Fig. S5A red bar), and from July to November 2021, the number of working-age individuals without vaccination records decreased to 1/5 (Fig. S5A purple bar).

Interval-specific mortality rates were calculated based on the number of deaths among individuals without vaccination records during that week. Notably, mortality rates among senior and working-age individuals without vaccination records rose significantly during periods of increased COVID-19 vaccination (Fig. S5C). The timing of increased mortality among individuals without vaccination records in senior or working-age populations appears unnatural, as it coincides with mass vaccination campaigns targeting each generation rather than external common factors such as the COVID-19 pandemic. This suggests that individuals without vaccination records are not necessarily unvaccinated, and that a significant proportion of those without records are actually vaccinated. The weekly average mortality rate for those without vaccination records was 0.0012% for the younger age group, 0.007% for the working-age group, and 0.098% for the senior group. Converted to annual rates, these figures amount to 0.06%, 0.36%, and 5.1%, respectively (Fig. S5D), which actually appear excessively high. However, this supports the idea that these individuals without vaccination records are not equivalent to the unvaccinated, but rather represent a situation where a significant proportion of vaccinated individuals' data has been contaminated into the smaller population without vaccination records.

Individuals without vaccination records might include those with misread OCR data, delayed municipal entries, or system errors preventing record reflection. Indeed, a scandal emerged in Japan, where the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare classified individuals with unknown vaccination history as unvaccinated for statistical purposes (14), revealing that the original unvaccinated count in those statistics was itself unknown. Consequently, precise mortality data for unvaccinated individuals could not be obtained even through this disclosure request.

Legends to Figures

Fig. S1. Number of vaccinated individuals by vaccination date (left) and number of deaths by days from final vaccination to death (right) for each vaccine variant. Periods with insufficient observation time are shaded gray.

Fig. S2. Excess deaths after COVID vaccine rollout in Japan. A. Annual observed and expected death counts in Japan. The expected line was estimated from annual death counts from 2010 through 2020 (prior to the start of COVID-19 vaccinations), excluding 2011, the year of the Great East Japan Earthquake(32). The equation for the expected line is $y = 18,189x - 35,352,675$. The R-squared value for the determining factor of the expected line is displayed. The 95% confidence interval is shown in the shaded region. **B.** Annual observed death counts, expected deaths, and excess deaths for 2020 (just before COVID-19 vaccinations) and 2021 through 2024 (after the start of COVID-19 vaccinations).

Fig. S3. Simple mortality rate and interval-specific mortality rate for the senior generation. Peaks of interval-specific mortality are highlighted with red triangles.

Fig. S4. Simple mortality rate and interval-specific mortality rate for all generations combined. Peaks of interval-specific mortality are highlighted with red triangles.

Fig. S5. Mortality rate among individuals without COVID-19 vaccination records. A. A decrease in the number of individuals without vaccination records across generations over time. The period of sharp decline in seniors without vaccination records (June to August 2021) is shown by the red bar, while the period of sharp decline in working-age individuals without vaccination records (July to November 2021) is indicated by the purple bar. **B.** Interval-specific mortality rates for individuals without vaccination records across all generations. **C.** Interval-specific mortality rates for individuals without vaccination records by generation. **D.** Annual mortality rates for individuals without vaccination records.

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